

CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS CAUSES AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT

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Abstract. This article is about the treatment of patients with congenital heart disease, the article talks about the types of congenital heart defects, their causes and complications observed in patients with the disease, treatment methods and measures aimed at their prevention.

Key words: dilatation, myocardial hypertrophy, cardiogenic shock, cardiac asthma, chronic heart failure (CHF), echocardiography, oxygen therapy.

Introduction

In recent years, many reforms have been implemented in the field of medicine in our Republic, as in other fields. In particular, he began to pay special attention to the health care system. Scientific centers, hospitals, family polyclinics equipped with all modern equipment have been established in our republic. Including, modern methods of treating patients with congenital heart defects were developed. With the use of modern technologies, operations for the treatment of very difficult and complex heart defects have been successfully carried out today. Today, more than 30 complex operations are being performed at the Republican Center for Cardiology. In addition, endovascular treatment of heart defects is gaining popularity. The uniqueness of these innovative procedures is that they are performed through a wrist vein without making a chest incision. For information, about 60% of deaths in the world are caused by diseases of the cardiovascular system. These types of diseases are one of the main causes of disability. The article discusses modern methods of treating patients with congenital heart disease.

The main part

As a result of the inability of the heart to perform its pumping function, a pathological process associated with the occurrence of blood circulation disorders in the organs occurs, resulting in heart failure. In recent years, births with congenital heart defects have increased compared to previous years. We can conditionally divide the main factors leading to heart failure into two large groups, these can be intra-cardiac and extra-cardiac diseases. Etiological factors cause a violation of contractility of the heart muscles and a violation of blood pumping, development of heart failure. Six factors mainly affect the development of congenital heart defects.

These are:

1. Anemia in pregnant women;
2. Chronic or acute infectious disease of a woman;
3. Viral diseases;
4. Hormonal factor
5. Neurohumoral factor
6. Marriage between close relatives.

An increase in the performance of the muscles of the enlarged part of the heart leads to their hypertrophy. This, in turn, causes the heart to work harder. During dilatation, the systolic pressure of the heart increases. Dilatation is the expansion of one or more chambers of the heart. In some cases, this expansion can be a compensatory (tonogenic dilatation) due to excessive load on this part, and in other cases it can be a sign of decompensation and a sharp decrease in myocardial contractility (myogenic dilatation).

There are many types and causes of congenital heart defects. In the development of heart failure, the general state of the body, brain, endocrine system and other various reflectors and effects are of great importance. Myocardial hypertrophy means an increase in the mass of the heart muscle as a result of excessive load. Congenital heart defects and congenital heart anomalies, also known as congenital heart disease, are defects in the structure of the heart or large vessels present at birth. Cardiogenic shock is one of the severe complications of myocardial infarction. It occurs as a result of disruption of the neuro-humoral control system and disruption of the vital activity of the organism. In cardiogenic shock, the pulse is thready or undetectable, and blood pressure is low. Cardiac asthma is an attack of intense wheezing that causes suffocation in a short period of time. Attacks occur more often at night when the patient is lying down. Suffocation slowly increases and begins to attack with coughing. After timely medical care, panting disappears.

Chronic heart failure affects 0.5% to 2% of the population, and its prevalence in people over 75 years old is about 10%. The urgency of the problem of heart failure is determined by the increasing number of patients suffering from it, high mortality and disability rates. Since heart failure is a secondary syndrome that develops as a result of certain diseases, diagnostic measures should be directed to early detection of the primary disease, even if there are no clear signs.

Signs:

- Vertebral anomalies

- Anal artesia
- Cardiovascular abnormalities
- Tracheoesophageal fistula
- Esophageal atresia
- Renal or radial abnormalities
- Defects in hands and feet

Classification of chronic heart failure recommended by the New York Cardiology Association:

Functional classes	Characteristics
Class I	Asymptomatic dysfunction of the left ventricle: physical activity is not limited in patients with heart disease
Class II	Mild heart failure: Physical activity is not limited in patients with heart disease.
Class III	Moderate heart failure: physical activity is significantly limited in patients with heart disease.
Class IV	Severe heart failure: patients with heart disease experience discomfort even with light exercise.

Modern methods of testing for congenital heart failure are very popular nowadays. For example, in electrocardiography, tachycardia, bradycardia, swinging arrhythmia and other rhythm and conduction disorders are recorded. Echocardiography reveals left ventricular dysfunction and local contractility disorders, accumulation of fluid between the pericardial sheets, their adhesion and thickening, and a number of other changes characteristic of the disease leading to chronic heart failure (CHF).

Methods of treatment of acute and chronic heart failure are carried out with the help of drugs and without drugs.

In the treatment without drugs, drinking fluids and limiting table salt, eating light and fast-digesting protein-rich foods, evening walks, breathing fresh air, following a daily routine, etc.

Treatment with the help of drugs is carried out taking into account the main disease that led to heart failure, its complications and delay.

To treat acute heart failure, oxygen therapy is carried out in order to increase blood saturation with oxygen. In the absence of contraindications, cardiac glycosides are prescribed in order to increase the contractility of the myocardium and in case of pronounced tachycardia and swinging arrhythmia. During the treatment of acute heart failure, systolic blood pressure is monitored every 1-2 minutes.

Congenital heart defects may require surgery and medication. Medications include diuretics, which help the body lose water, salts, and dioxin to make the heart contract harder.

Measures such as early detection of the main diseases leading to congenital heart defects, treatment and prevention of its complications are included. Regular monitoring of patients with this disease slows down the progression of the disease. More than 1.8 million people live with congenital heart defects.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is necessary to treat patients with congenital heart defects using new modern methods, to carry out procedures for early detection of the disease, and to develop and implement new modern methods in the future.

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